

METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE BY USING MULTIMEDIA PROGRAMS

KASSYMBEKOVA AINUR TALGARBEKKYZY

senior teacher, chair of foreign languages, Kazakh National Research Technical university
named after K.I.Satpayev
Almaty, Kazakhstan

AKIMBEKOVA SHYRYN ADILKAIROVNA

PhD, chair of foreign languages, Abai Kazakh National Pedagogical
University, Almaty, Kazakhstan

ARYSTANBEKOVA BAGDAT AKISHOVNA

senior teacher, chair of Practical English, Abai Kazakh National Pedagogical University,
Almaty, Kazakhstan

ALIPOVA ASSEM TOKTARBAYEVNA

senior teacher, chair of Practical English, Abai Kazakh National Pedagogical
University, Almaty, Kazakhstan

Annotation. *The article discusses the role of multimedia in modern education, emphasizing its advantages over traditional teaching methods. Multimedia lessons combine audio, video, animation, graphics, and digital tools to enhance students' perception and engagement. The concept of edutainment highlights the balance between learning and entertainment, making the process more effective and motivating. Multimedia tools enrich learning by engaging multiple senses, promoting cooperation, active participation, self-study, and communication skills. The shift from teacher-centered to student-centered approaches is presented as the core of the new learning model supported by multimedia technologies.*

Keywords: *multimedia, education, edutainment, learning process, student-centered learning, teaching technologies, cooperation, communication competence, self-study, modern teaching methods*

Multimedia is any visual representation that has a combination of audio, video, animation or graphics. Multimedia, as a rule, is more pleasant and informative for perception than just text. Previously, a lesson was called multimedia if it included a teacher's story, a tape recording, a movie, slides and any technical means of teaching. Today, a "multimedia" lesson means a lesson using a multimedia training program, a computer or laptop, a projector, a webcam. There are even several modern areas of research in the theory of learning, in particular, the theory of multimedia learning.

Edutainment reflects the connection between learning and entertainment, that is, the student focuses on the learning process, while having entertainment goals.

It is multimedia tools that have the strongest impact on students. They enrich the learning process, make it possible to make learning more effective by involving most of the sensory components of the learner in the process of perception of educational information. They have become an objective reality of our time, and a foreign language teacher simply cannot fail to take advantage of the opportunities they provide for teaching real communication in a foreign language. Along with multimedia technologies, a new ideology of thinking came to the school. According to the previously accepted model of teaching at the school, there was a teacher in the center of learning technology; there was an unspoken competition between students; students played a passive role in the classroom; the essence of learning was the transfer of knowledge (facts).

The new learning model that replaces it is based on the following provisions: at the center of learning technology is the student; at the heart of learning activities is cooperation; students play an

active role in learning; the essence of technology is the development of the ability to self-study and the communicative competence of students.

The main groups of tasks solved with the help of multimedia in English lessons include:

- supporting students' academic work;
- ensuring real communication with native speakers;
- ensuring access of all participants in the educational process to rapidly growing information funds stored in centralized information systems;
- developing cognitive interest and motivation to learn English.

The main purposes of the multimedia lesson are:

- the study of new material;
- the presentation of new information and the expansion of the horizons of students;
- the consolidation of what has been passed;
- the development of educational skills and abilities;
- the repetition of the studied material;
- the practical application of the acquired knowledge, skills;
- generalization and systematization of knowledge.

What are the main ways to use the capabilities of modern multimedia technologies in teaching a foreign language? For example:

- the use of ready-made software products for learning a foreign language, delivered mainly on CD-ROMs;
- application of software products created directly by teachers (or teachers together with students) in various tool environments or visual design environments);
- use of Internet resources.

With the help of educational programs, it is possible to significantly change the ways of managing educational activities, purposefully manage the competitive element present in the activities of students, individualize learning, and this contributes to improving the quality of learning.

Multimedia presentations can be anywhere where there is a computer and a projector or another local playback device. The broadcast of the presentation can be either "live" or pre-recorded.

1. When studying new material. Allows you to illustrate with a variety of visual means. The application is especially beneficial in cases where it is necessary to show the dynamics of the development of a process.

2. When fixing a new theme.

3. To test knowledge. Computer testing is self-examination and self-realization, it is a good incentive for learning, it is a way of activity and self-expression. For a teacher, it is a means of quality control of knowledge, a programmed way of accumulating grades.

4. To deepen knowledge, as an additional material for lessons.

5. When checking the front independent work. Provides visual control of the results along with oral.

6. When solving problems of a training nature. Helps to perform and monitor the intermediate and final results of independent work.

The teacher can use a bank of ready-made multimedia presentations created by colleagues and posted on professional websites and forums, which significantly reduces energy consumption in preparation for the lesson. Or he creates his own presentation for a specific lesson or topic. The value of the presentations created by the teacher is that the material in them is given to students compactly, in the right sequence; there is nothing superfluous in it, everything "works" to achieve the goals and objectives of a particular lesson, unlike ready-made films and slides. In addition, the presentation material is clearly timed, from an informative and lexical point of view, it corresponds to the topic of the lesson as much as possible. Teachers of our gymnasium have created a bank of multimedia presentations on many topics of English grammar, vocabulary, country studies, etc., which are regularly used by all teachers in the classroom-lesson system, and there are new models of using multimedia presentations in extracurricular activities.

Multimedia Internet resource is an Internet resource in which basic information is presented in the form of multimedia. This is a modern and very convenient mechanism that does not replace the performance of classical functions, but complements and expands the range of services and opportunities for all visitors.

Multimedia Internet resources are characterized by the following: they can contain various types of information (not only text, but also sound, graphic, animation, video, etc.), a high degree of clarity of materials, authenticity of materials, entertaining, independence, instant feedback. Currently, a methodology for teaching a foreign language using the Internet is being developed. There are supporters of the idea of teaching a language only using the Internet, as well as supporters of traditional work with a textbook. But most English language teachers, including in our gymnasium, prefer to use the Internet along with traditional teaching tools, integrating it into the educational process.

The simplest application of the Internet is this is to use it as a source of additional materials and exercises, both for the teacher and for the student when studying, repeating, fixing or controlling any topic or when preparing for the UNT (Unified national testing). Here are just some of the Internet resources we use in the lessons:

<https://itest.kz/ru> - The main goal of this project is to prepare students for the successful passing of the Unified National Testing (UNT) in an accessible and interesting form.

The test tasks of this site were prepared by teachers and methodologists-consultants who participated in the preparation of test tasks for the UNT.

ITest consists of test tasks for each subject with answers. Additionally, there are summaries of review lectures and the opportunity to work on errors.

The electronic complex will help you prepare and successfully pass tests in each subject. Also, this training complex makes it possible to pass UNT trial tests on the subjects studied in conditions as close as possible to real testing.

<https://bilimland.kz/kk> - An innovative company forming a new e-learning market for Kazakhstan. We are engaged in the development, localization and distribution of educational content, as well as related technologies and services. Among our clients there are state organizations, the largest IT companies, media structures and leading educational institutions of the country.

<https://www.native-english.ru/> - Everything you need when learning English is a grammar guide, tests, a dictionary of idioms and proverbs, songs, poems and much more.

<https://usefulenglish.ru/idioms/> - The training materials with exercises on this site describe the use of standard literate English, i.e. the language of general use in its standard usage. Examples of usage, words and phrases, idioms and stable expressions in various situations in oral and written speech are given.

https://www.english-test.net/toEIC/listening/the_bund_shanghai.html - This site presents a large collection of audio files for listening to foreign language speech, as well as exercises for practicing pronunciation.

Today, multimedia technologies are one of the promising areas of informatization of the educational process. The prospect of successful application of modern information technologies in education is seen in the improvement of software and methodological support, the material base, as well as in the mandatory professional development of the teaching staff. All the listed properties of multimedia programs help to solve the main task of language education, defined by the Program on foreign languages — the formation of students' different competencies and communicative competence in particular.

At the present stage of informatization of education, which is characterized by the transition to a qualitatively new level associated with the active use of information technology in the educational process, one of the priority areas of informatization of education is the implementation of didactic capabilities of multimedia technologies in the teaching of various educational subjects.

In the first chapter, we emphasized the need to use information technology in the process of teaching a foreign language. The use of individual components or ready-made electronic publications

for educational purposes, electronic educational tools, computer training programs in a foreign language allows for automated control and self-monitoring of learning outcomes, computer visualization of educational foreign language information by visual representation of lexical, grammatical and phonetic material.

The study of scientific and methodological works in the field of the use of ICT tools in the process of teaching a foreign language allows us to distinguish three main approaches:

- 1) integrated use of ICT tools at various stages of the lesson;
- 2) partial use of ready-made electronic publications for educational purposes in the educational process;
- 3) the use of applied and instrumental software tools for the development of author's applications.

At the same time, it should be noted that the third approach is of particular importance, in which the teacher has the opportunity to implement his own methodological ideas of presenting educational material, automate the processes of adapting the content of educational material to the age and individual characteristics of students, use the author's structure of the teaching content, modify his methodological and software developments, automate the processes of monitoring learning outcomes. This approach is closely intertwined with the first two approaches. After the author's programs and lessons are developed, the teacher can conduct them using a set of multimedia tools or based on ready-made training programs. In the following chapters, we will analyze the online programs used in teaching English and consider a lesson based on one of them.

At the present stage of informatization of education, which is characterized by the transition to a qualitatively new level associated with the active use of information technology in the educational process, one of the priority areas of informatization of education is the implementation of didactic capabilities of multimedia technologies in the teaching of various educational subjects

Teaching foreign languages requires a teacher of high skill and excellent knowledge of the material in order to hold the attention of listeners, to interest and involve them in the discussion of various problematic issues. It is multimedia technologies that make it possible to present language material not only visually, but also interestingly and more intelligibly. They allow you to avoid boring and monotonous presentation of the material. Now I will highlight several modern tools for interactive work in the audience.

Google Classroom

Google Classroom or Google Classroom is an online service for online learning. Allows you to create courses, conduct webinars and test students.

In fact, Google has collected several of its tools in one service. Among them, a disk for storing files, Google Docs for publishing text lectures, presentations, surveys, a service for video meetings and a calendar for planning training.

Google Classroom is completely in Russian. Suitable for schools and universities. In the article we will analyze the capabilities of the service, its advantages and disadvantages. The service is available for free

To open your virtual classroom, just create a Google account. Immediately after that, you will be able to add students, create a course or test, as well as conduct a webinar.

Sky Smart platform:

- Spoken English

The platform uses its own techniques that help to overcome the language barrier.

- Exams

The platform prepares for school exams based on materials that have been approved by the Ministry of Education.

- School curriculum

The platform helps to find gaps, improve knowledge and improve grades

Yaklass Platform

Yaklass is an educational online resource for schoolchildren, students, teachers and parents. Started working in 2014. Today, the online platform is used by 12 million users from 50,000 schools in Russia, Austria, Armenia, Belarus, Germany, India, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Uzbekistan, Finland. The portal contains online simulators for the school curriculum and an automatic check of homework.

Internet Lesson Platform

InternetUrok is the largest comprehensive online school from grades 1 to 11 and a library of video tutorials and other materials on the school curriculum.

In the Library you can find materials on the main subjects of the school curriculum:

- 5000+ up-to-date video tutorials;
- 4300+ notes;
- 6300+ tests;
- 8200+ simulators.

It is known that teaching foreign languages is based on such general didactic principles as visibility, accessibility, feasibility, individualization, consciousness. As information technologies, in particular multimedia, introduced into the educational process, of all the above principles, visibility realized to the greatest extent.

The search for optimal ways in the organization of the educational process is the main task of any teacher. And preference, of course, is given to developing methods. Each teacher has different technologies that make learning effective, entertaining, and interesting. And currently, foreign language classes cannot be imagined without the use of multimedia presentations.

One of the main advantages of multimedia technologies in teaching foreign languages can be safely attributed to the visualization of the submitted material. All information can be presented both in audio and visual form.

Psychologists have long proved that a person perceives most of the information visually. Only 10-20% of people can perceive text information quickly and effectively.

It should be noted that the indisputable trend of the modern stage of informatization of education is the universal desire to integrate various electronic learning tools, such as electronic reference books, encyclopedias, training programs, automated control of students' knowledge, computer textbooks and simulators into unified software and methodological complexes, considered as educational electronic publications and resources.

In recent years, due to the development of new multimedia technologies, the activity of using personal computers in the educational process at all levels has significantly increased. The computer is increasingly seen as an "assistant" teacher trying to activate and individualize the learning process, increase the effectiveness of knowledge control.

Multimedia technologies are new information technologies that provide work with animated computer graphics and text, speech and high-quality sound, still images and moving video images. If we structure the information with which multimedia technologies can work, then we can say that multimedia is a synthesis of three elements: digital information (text, graphics, animation), analog visual display information (video, photos, paintings, etc.) and analog information (speech, music, other sounds).

Pedagogical software tools are the main part of the computer software and methodological complex, which includes, in addition to pedagogical software tools, methodological and didactic support of these programs.

Currently, there is no single classification of pedagogical software tools, although in many works, depending on the methodological goals, the implementation of which justifies the introduction of such tools, the following types are distinguished among them:

- training programs are designed to form and consolidate skills and abilities, as well as for self-training of trainees;
- monitoring programs designed to control a certain level of knowledge and skills;
- mentoring programs that focus primarily on the assimilation of new concepts;

- demonstration programs designed for visual demonstration of educational material of a descriptive nature;
- information and reference programs are designed to display the necessary information;
- simulation and modeling programs designed to "simulate" objects and phenomena;
- programs for problem-based learning, which are based mainly on the ideas and principles of cognitive psychology, they provide indirect management of students' activities. This means that a variety of tasks are presented and students are encouraged to solve them through trial and error.

In the course of the work, an analysis of the use of information technologies in teaching English was carried out. To develop a lesson summary, an analysis of technical means, software, and theoretical material on the English language used in school.

The following software was used in the preparation of video lectures:

- «ZOOM»
- «Microsoft Teams»

Advantages of Zoom:

- A large number of participants. The webinar via zoom involves active interaction with the general public. Already on the free version, you can organize an online event with up to 100 users.

- Multiplatform. It is easy to get to the conference via an invitation link through your browser from any device, even from a smartphone. At the same time, you do not need to specifically install the program \ application.

- High quality video and sound. An important indicator of zoom's evaluation as a platform for webinars!

- No delays and interference. The versatility does not affect the operation of the program. Interference with communication is usually associated with poor Internet connection of users, and not with the problems of the site.

- Screen demonstration. For the sake of clarity of the event, the free version offers several options for working with the screen. In order for the participants to see the materials of the presenter, he needs to have administrator rights.

- Visualization. During the speech, you can make visible the movement of the cursor on the screen. And also complement the presentation with text, diagrams, drawing elements. The drawn fragments are easy to delete, move and save.

- Continue the webinar on another platform. If you need to draw a lot, then you can continue to conduct a zoom webinar on your iPad - just connect from another device.

- Built-in chat. A great opportunity to have a conversation with the participants without interrupting the speaker. The organizer and participants can write messages for everyone, as well as correspond with each other. In addition, there is a chat with yourself, where it is convenient to copy notes, photos, videos, audio and store materials for 10 years. If the chat correspondence contains important data, it can be saved as a separate file.

- Feedback. The built-in "raise your hand" function will let you know that someone has any questions or suggestions during the speech. With the help of "reaction" stickers, you can show a personal attitude to what you have said or seen. And the presenter will also understand that he is really being listened to.

- Conference recording. It is easy to record and save the progress of the event, pause and continue recording from a certain point.

- Managing speakers. The administrator has the ability to turn off the microphones of all participants in the conference and leave the sound only for the speakers.

- Session halls. In order to discuss something with some participants and not distract others, you can create separate halls right during the event and group them. The function is disabled by default in the free version, it is easy to enable it in the service settings on the website.

- Invitations. To invite to an event, it is enough to copy the direct link of the created conference and send it to the recipients in any way: by message, via mail or social networks.

The disadvantage of Zoom:

- Duration. The “Basic” tariff assumes unlimited communication with only one person. Time is limited for the maximum number of users (up to 100 people). After forty minutes, the video call session will end and you will have to re-create the conference, as well as invite participants to it. The “Professional” tariff removes such duration restrictions, and also includes a cloud for storing recorded conferences.

- Number of speakers. Initially, only one person can be the organizer. To appoint more moderators, you need to purchase such a feature.

Advantages of Microsoft Teams:

- There is a place to store files for work

Unlike the free version of Zoom, the free Office 365 plan already includes access to 1 TB of cloud storage. All projects and documents will be automatically saved in the cloud.

- Detailed guide in Russian

To study the guide for working with Microsoft Teams, follow the link. The document explains the purpose of each button and gives advice on the organization of the educational process. In addition, there are instructional videos on working with Microsoft Teams and auxiliary applications for teachers. Videos in English, to understand enough basic knowledge of English. Or watch this playlist in Russian.

- Quickly organize an online conference

Video conferences are also available in other applications, but in Microsoft Teams it is easy to schedule them through a calendar, set up a notification inside the platform or by mail, and to quickly connect a student to a lesson or a parent to a meeting, you need to mention his name via @.

- It is convenient to distribute tasks

You can take a test, work with a digital whiteboard, and share information from your screen without leaving the application. In the Tasks tab, the teacher creates a task in the form of a document, table or presentation, or you can download a ready-made one from OneDrive or a computer.

- The routine verification process will be brought to automatism

Microsoft Teams have provided all possible scenarios for which the school teacher checks the work. And all the estimates are easy to export to Excel.

The disadvantage of Microsoft Teams:

- The platform works with errors

According to user reviews, the platform works unevenly, downloads files incorrectly for a long time, and can disable the entire device system.

Does not work with DOC, XLS and PPT files

- Documents, tables, presentations will need to be translated into the current format — docx, xlsx, pptx, respectively.

- Not the simplest functionality

Due to the large number of functions of the platform, it takes a long time to understand its work. We'll have to waste time.

Advantages of Quizizz Platform:

- The Quiz platform makes it possible to create online quizzes, tests and surveys for free and accessible. Students can answer tests created by the teacher from tablets, laptops, smartphones, from any device with Internet access.;

- convenient and simple registration form;

- low time costs when creating your own applications (no more than 15 minutes);

- automatic verification of works and ranking with the results;

- an exciting non-traditional form of education for children;

- the ability of students to work with tasks without registration, which ensures accessibility and significantly saves time (the exception is the Control work mode).

The disadvantage of Quizizz Platform:

When organizing individual work, it is impossible to be sure that each student will have a smartphone or tablet with Internet access at hand.

(In this case, you can organize a team or pair work).

Advantages of Google Classroom

- The service is available for free
- Several people can work in the service at once
- Online courses in Google Classroom are easy to create

If there are no ready-made materials, you can create from scratch. To do this, the service has built-in tools: a Word-type text editor, presentations, assignments and tests.

- Each course can be beautifully designed — add a title cover. This is where the design possibilities end.

- The course is divided into theory and practice. Theory is all the lecture materials that you have added to the training program.

- As a practice, you can use assignments and online tests so that students consolidate the studied material.

The disadvantage of Google Classroom

- Learning opportunities are limited. Google Classroom allows you to create courses that are more like electronic textbooks: with text lectures, video tutorials, presentations, tests and assignments.

Here you will not be able to create a course with game elements, a dialogue simulator for practicing communication skills or an interactive video.

Even if you buy additional computer programs and collect content in them, it won't work in Google Classroom. This is because the service does not support the world standards of electronic courses: SCORM, cmi 5, Tin Can (api).

- There are no polls in the free version, as well as the "Raise your hand" function. If the listener wants to ask a question, you will have to write to the chat. There are no other possibilities.

- You can't turn off the microphone for students in the settings so that they don't mess around and disrupt the lesson. There is no such possibility in Google Classroom.

- The possibilities for design are limited. The only thing that is available is to choose a cover for the course from the suggested ones. You cannot change fonts, background color, or buttons.

- There is no protection against cheating in the tests. It is impossible to limit the time for the answer and the number of attempts, to fine for mistakes or to start mixing questions so that they are displayed in random order for each student. The tests themselves are more like surveys.

The use of multimedia teaching tools is a natural stage in the development of pedagogical technologies. Currently, there are many multimedia learning tools available. They are designed for teaching speech activities: reading, writing, listening, speaking; explaining and repeating various grammatical material with appropriate tasks and exercises, both for independent learning and group work. The use of multimedia presentations in lessons on the development of communication skills has a number of advantages. One of the main The advantage is the ability to provide students with correct answers in writing after completing tasks. It is possible to invite students to write down some facts, phrases, sentences, based on visibility, which makes it easier for many students to write correctly. And in the future, these recordings can be used for discussions and monologue statements on the topic, as well as when doing homework. Another positive result of using presentations is a faster pace of the lesson, the interest of students. The teacher can use developments created independently, for example, presentations in PowerPoint. This program is also convenient when performing creative project work by students with subsequent demonstration to the audience. The advantages of project work have been known for a long time and are used in the teaching methods of various school subjects, including a foreign language. Traditionally, the study of a topic or section ends with repetition, consolidation and generalization. All these elements can be combined by inviting students at the final stage of each topic to create a multimedia project. Creating a presentation, students are given a great opportunity to systematize the acquired knowledge and skills, their practical application, as well as the opportunity to realize intellectual potential and abilities. It is very important for students to feel interest in independent creative work, to feel the significance of the results of their

work, because the presentation is a ready-made methodological material for the lesson, as well as to feel their own success. When developing lessons, teachers often face a problem the absence of a handout with tasks. This problem can be solved with the help of multimedia presentations. The content of presentations can be different: a video series-a hint, additional information, text tasks, diagrams, tables. Thus, the use of information and communication technologies makes learning fun, allows for more interesting and visual presentation of educational material, as well as motivating students to study this material independently.

CONCLUSION

In this article, the problem of the introduction of information technologies in the process of teaching foreign languages was considered. As a result of the study, it was revealed that the process of using new technologies in the classroom is at an initial stage. The modern education system does not keep up with the development of technological progress.

The main functions and possibilities of using modern information tools were analyzed. The complex use of new technological achievements with the latest computer programs undoubtedly gives a positive end result. A lesson using computer technology arouses great interest among students, makes them more independent. Upon graduation, students will not only possess a knowledge base, but will also meet the requirements of a modern technically advanced society.

When working with computer technologies, the role of the teacher is changing, whose task is to support and guide the development of students' personality, their creative search. Relationships with students are based on the principles of cooperation and joint creativity.

The effectiveness of the use of information technologies was confirmed during a foreign language lesson using computer learning tools in the 5th grade of secondary school.

Properly organized work of students with a computer can contribute to the growth of their cognitive and communicative interest, which in turn will contribute to the activation and expansion of opportunities for independent work of students to master a foreign language, both in the classroom and outside of school hours.

REFERENCES

1. Pomerantseva N.G. The use of Internet resources in teaching French // Collection of scientific papers of Moscow State University, 2008. pp.75-78.
2. Tevs D.P. The use of modern information and communication technologies in the educational process. Educational and methodical manual. Barnaul: BSPU, 2006. pp. 5-7.
3. Vladimirova L. P. Internet in foreign language lessons // Foreign languages at school. Moscow:Prosveshchenie, 2002. No. 3. pp. 39-41.
4. Karamysheva T.V. Learning foreign languages using a computer (in questions and answers). Saint Petersburg: Soyuz, 2001. pp. 14-19.
5. Andreeva O.A. Learning foreign languages using computer technologies // Materials of the festival of pedagogical ideas "Open lesson". www.festival .1september.ru. 2006
6. Vaseyko D.N. The use of an interactive whiteboard at school // Materials of the festival of pedagogical ideas "Open Lesson". www.festival .1september.ru.
7. Anishina T.P. Interactive whiteboard HITACHI StarBoard // Handbook of the head of an educational institution. Moscow: ICFER Educational Resources, 2009. No. 11. p.101.
8. Apatova N.V. Information technologies in school education. M.: Enlightenment, 1994.
9. Galishnikova E.M. The use of an interactive Smart-board in the learning process // Teacher, 2007. No. 4. pp. 8-10.
10. Zakharova I.G. Information technologies in education. Textbook for students of higher pedagogical educational institutions. Moscow: Academy, 2003. pp. 25-29.
11. Ksenzova G.Y. Promising school technologies. Moscow: Pedagogical Society of Russia, 2000.
12. Mashbits E.I. Computerization of education: problems and prospects. M.: Pedagogy, 1986.
13. Nelunova E.D. Information and communication technologies in teaching a foreign language at school. Yakutsk: IPKRO, 2006. p.104.
14. Nikolayko E.Z. The use of ICT in English lessons // Materials of the festival of pedagogical ideas "Open Lesson". www. festival.1september.ru.
15. Petrova L.P. The use of computers in foreign language lessons - the need for time // Foreign languages at school. Moscow: Prosveshchenie, 2005. No. 5.
16. Polat E.S. Internet in extracurricular work in a foreign language // Foreign language at school. Moscow: Prosveshchenie, 2001. No. 5. pp. 40-43.
17. Polat E.S. Internet in foreign language lessons // Foreign languages at school. Moscow: Prosveshchenie, 2001. No. 2. pp. 14-20.
18. Robert I.V. Theory and methodology of informatization of education (psychological, pedagogical and technological aspects). Moscow: ИО РАО, 2007. pp. 7-10.
19. Sinegubova N.M. Information technologies in English lessons // School, 2006. No. 2. pp. 43-44.